

COGNITIVE-PRAGMATIC STUDY OF MODAL WORDS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Abstract: Studying the pragmatic and cognitive properties of modal words in Uzbek and English is the goal of this project. The study examines the many purposes and interpretations of modal terms in two languages, highlighting contextual and cultural variations. In language learning and cross-cultural communication, this approach aids in determining the role of modal words.

Keywords: Cognitive research, pragmatic analysis, modal terms, English and Uzbek language, semantics, meaning, linguistics, cultural context, cognitive linguistics, communicative aim, language logic, modal functions, and contextual influence.

In any language, modal words are a powerful tool for conveying ideas and opinions. They also allow the speaker to communicate their subjective perspective on reality. The speaker uses modal words like uncertainty, likelihood, confidence, condition, and possibility to convey his opinions. The content of modal words in Uzbek and English is different, and by examining the pragmatic and semantic elements of both languages, one may comprehend how these modal words are constructed and utilized differently depending on linguistic and cultural settings. This study aims to identify the characteristics of modal terms that are similar and different between the two languages.

Language researchers are very interested in the significance and cognitive function of modal words. Modal expressions are the primary means by which the meaning conveyed by the speaker to the listener during language learning can be understood. With its unique cognitive load, each modal word tells the listener about the speaker's beliefs, presumptions, and degree of confidence. Modal words like "may," "could," and "must," for instance, allow the speaker to convey his attitude toward reality on a variety of levels in English. The cognitive distinction between modal words is demonstrated by the fact that "may" denotes probability and "must" denotes certainty. In the Uzbek language, however, comparable terms like "possible," "necessary," and "necessary" also convey possibility, necessity, or assurance.. Such similarities in the appearance of modal words in English and Uzbek languages are important in the successful implementation of communicative goals between the speaker and the listener.

When it comes to communicating in the language and conveying speech intents, the pragmatic usage of modal words is crucial. Modal words in Uzbek and English give the speaker the chance to show respect for the audience, soften his remarks, or convey uncertainty. For instance, even when the speaker is making a request, phrases like "could you please..." convey respect in English. In the Uzbek language, the speaker uses phrases like "please" and "mukminmi" to give his statements a pragmatic context. This demonstrates how

modal words in both languages employ particular rules and carry out intricate pragmatic functions during conversation.

It is also important to examine how modal words are used to convey probability and purpose. The modal phrases “intent,” “probability,” and “assumption” are used in both Uzbek and English to convey the speaker’s degree of confidence. For instance, in English, a speaker can use words like “may,” “might,” and “must” to convey varying degrees of confidence. The words “may” and “must” stand for likelihood and high degree of certainty, respectively. Words like “possible,” “necessary,” and “required” are also crucial in the Uzbek language for conveying the speaker’s degree of certainty and plausibility.

Despite the similarity between these linguistic units, their use in the two languages differs in certain pragmatic and cognitive ways. For instance, the Uzbek term “kerak” can convey a particular likelihood or presumption in addition to being frequently used to convey necessity or obligation. A few modal words in English help to communicate such notions more clearly.

According to cognitive theory, the speaker’s degree of knowledge and reality perception also influence the choice of modal terms. By selecting modal terms, the speaker cognitively attempts to increase the effectiveness of his speech because every language has a unique cognitive experience and cultural background. Examples of modal words used in Uzbek are “kerak” and “lozim,” but in English, the speaker attempts to convey his objective or belief by using words like “must” or “have to.” By using cognitive models to determine the meaning of these modal words, both languages enable the speaker to express themselves effectively.

The usage of modal terms may vary depending on particular cultural values and communicative practices in each language when examined from a cultural perspective. For instance, the speaker of English attempts to convey himself in a courteous and respectful manner by using a lot of modal terms. The speaker utilizes modal words to convey gentleness and grace in his discourse because social norms and rules of respect are highly respected in this society. This feature is also present in the Uzbek language, albeit occasionally certain modal expressions that are unique to Uzbek culture might not quite match the pragmatic usage of English. For example, in Uzbek, certain instructions can be given using words like “necessary” or “kerak”, but when it is necessary to soften them, phrases like “mukminmi” or “iltimos” are added. This change is adapted to cultural norms and the pragmatic use of language.

The study’s findings are crucial for understanding the unique characteristics of modal terms in Uzbek and English as well as their cognitive and pragmatic usage. An examination of modal words from a cognitive and pragmatic standpoint aids in comprehending their cultural perceptions. These modal discrepancies between Uzbek and English can occasionally lead to miscommunications between the speaker and the listener and other people. As a result, both translators and language learners greatly benefit from taking into account modal words’ meanings and functions.

In conclusion, there are clear cognitive and pragmatic distinctions between the two languages’ modals, indicating that there are parallels and divergences between their semantic and cultural differences.

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